

Torrefaction of pulp industry sludge: Experimental validation, opportunities and challenges

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Pulp industry is known to produce large quantities of sludge. Sustainable handling of such large quantities of sludge is needed in order to improve the environmental feasibility of the pulp mills and to improve the resource efficiency. On the other hand, recently, under COP26, several countries agreed to phase-out coal from energy systems. In terms of fuel characteristics, torrefied biomass could be an alternative to coal. However, torrefied biomass pellets selling price is significantly higher than coal because of the increased raw material costs. Thus, using low cost organic residues such as pulp sludge could be help to optimize the economic feasibility of the torrefied pellets.

In this study, torrefaction of dewatered pulp industry sludge was studied in a bench scale continuous torrefaction reactor at 250, 275 and 300 °C. The influence of torrefaction treatment on composition and fuel characteristics of the sludge was established. The heating value of the sludge increased from 19 MJ/kg for dried to 22 MJ/kg for torrefied at 300 °C. The dried sludge contained 14 wt.% of hemicellulose, 33 wt.% of cellulose and 15 wt.% of lignin. As expected, torrefaction treatment showed significant effect on the biomass components present in the sludge. For example, at a torrefaction temperature of 300 °C hemicellulose was degraded completely and cellulose content was reduced to 66 wt.%. The fuel ratio of the torrefied sludge varied between 0.27 - 0.61. The ash melting behavior of the pulp industry sludge followed a similar pattern with agricultural wastes i.e. straw. The initial deformation temperature for dried sludge varied between 720 - 769 °C. The ash mainly contained SiO₂, Na₂O and CaO. The theoretical evaluation of several slagging and fouling indexes such as fouling index, acid/base ratio, and bed agglomeration index showed that the ash related issues of the sludge in the medium range.

Torrefaction treatment improved the fuel characteristics of the sludge and torrefied sludge can be compared with low rank coal such as lignite. The high initial moisture content could increase the overall energy input. The low ash melting temperatures could be a threat to combustion equipment. Finally, to conclude, torrefaction of pulp industry sludge can improve the environmental feasibility and generate additional revenue to the pulp mills.

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